

World News of Natural Sciences

An International Scientific Journal

WNOFNS 46 (2023) 14-29

EISSN 2543-5426

Effect of Green Manure on Soil Infiltration Rate, Soil Moisture Retention of Desert Plain Soils and Wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) Yield in the Northern State, Sudan

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ABSTRACT

This the study was conducted for two successive seasons 2014/15 and 2015/16 on a desert soil with the aim to investigate the effect of green manure on infiltration rate and soil moisture retention of desert soil and wheat yield in the Northern State of Sudan as well. Four types of green manure *Vigna radiate* (Green gram), *Vigna sinensis* (Cowpea), *Dolichos lablab* (Lablab bean) and *Sesbania canabina* (Sesbania pea) were selected as green manure corps with three levels. The first level was a seed rate of 12 kg ha⁻¹, 18 kg ha⁻¹, 24 kg ha⁻¹, 12 kg ha⁻¹ respectively. The second level was two times of the first level and third level was three times of the first level. The treatments were arranged in a randomized complete block design with three replications. The results showed that the effect of green manure was effective in improving the soil physical properties under investigation. The green manure application decreased soil infiltration rate on the average across the two seasons varied from 3.5 cm hr⁻¹ for the control to 1.7 cm hr⁻¹ (105 %) in the green manure treatments except lablab bean treatments, and improved the soil moisture retention as well and also, increased available water on the average across both seasons varied form 17 mm in the control to 27.6mm (58 %) in the green manure treatments except lablab bean treatments. The result also showed that the effect of green manure obtained very highly significantly ($P \leq 0.001$) increase in the grain yield of wheat on the average across the two seasons varied from 0.71 ton ha⁻¹ in the control treatment to 3.21 ton ha⁻¹ (352 %) in the green manure treatments except lablab bean treatments. It is recommended that Green gram (12 kg ha⁻¹), Cowpea (18 kg ha⁻¹) and Sesbania pea (12 kg ha⁻¹) which are available and cheaper are suitable types of green manure crops for soil reclamation of the desert plain soils of Sudan.

Keywords: desert plain soil, green manure, wheat, New Hamdab, *Triticum aestivum*

1. INTRODUCTION

The beneficial effects of organic matter for physical properties are: Improved soil aggregation, water holding capacity, soil porosity, infiltration rate; it decreased bulk density and crusting phenomenon of soil surface (Ali, 2001). Regular addition of organic manures such as animal manures, green manures and crop residues is very important in maintaining the tilth, fertility and productivity of agricultural soils, and in protecting them from wind and water erosion, and preventing nutrient losses through runoff and leaching (Hornik and Parr, 1987).

Rawls *et al.* (2003) studied the effect of soil organic carbon on soil water retention. They used the U.S. National Soil Characterization database and the database from pilot studies on soil quality as affected by long-term management. They found that increase in organic matter content led to increase of water retention in sandy soils, and to a decrease in fine-textured soils. At high organic carbon values, all soils showed an increase in water retention. The largest increase was in sandy and silty soils. Results are expressed as equations that can be used to evaluate the effect of the carbon sequestration and management practices on soil hydraulic properties.

Ahmed (2010) evaluated the effect of green and farmyard manures on the properties of desert plain soil in Northern Sudan. His study showed that each of the tested manures was effective in improving the soil physical properties. The grain yield of wheat crop was high to very highly significantly increased in response to the application of each of the green and farmyard manures.

Khalid *et al.* (2014) investigated the influence of poultry manure and NPK fertilizer on the hydraulic properties of sandy soil in Ghana. Their study showed that poultry manure was improved the hydrological properties of the sandy soil. The significant decreases in water entry (infiltration rate) and movement suggest that poultry manure application can minimize excessive leaching of plant nutrients in sandy soil.

Mosavi *et al.* (2012) studied the effect of different green manure application under dry land condition on some soil physical properties at a research station of dry land agriculture research institute in Maragheh, Iran. They reported that green manure application effects were significant on the soil aggregate stability, soil bulk density and available soil water

Rasul *et al.* (2015) found that organic manure had significantly increased plant height, length of spike, number of grains per spike, number of tillers per plant, 1000- grains weight, biological yield ,grain yield and harvest index.

In a study at Northern State of Sudan, Ahmed *et al.* (2011) evaluated the effect of green manure (GM) and farmyard manure (FYM) on wheat yield and yield components for two successive seasons (2007/08 and 2008/09). They found that each of GM and FYM had significant effects on the grain yield and yield components of wheat. In the Northern State of Sudan animal population is small which means that manures are not abundant. Moreover, sugar schemes lie far away to the south and east of the country that makes it impossible and economically irrational to transport northwards their organic products like baggasse, filter mud and cane trash (Ahmed, 2010). Hence, green manuring may pose a solution to the problem of

unavailability of soil amendments. This study was conducted with the aim to assess the effect of green manure on soil infiltration rate, soil moisture retention and wheat yield in desert soils.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The experiment was carried out during the two successive seasons 2014/15 and 2015/16 at the National Institute of Desert Studies Research Farm, New Hamdab Scheme, in the Northern State of Sudan. The study area lies at the intersection of latitude 17° 55' N, and longitude 31° 10' E in the desert climate.

The soil of the study area belongs to El Multaga soil series which classified as Vertic Haplocambids, fine loamy, mixed, supper active, hyperthermic. The soil structure is moderate subangular blocky. It is non-saline $E_{Ce} \geq 4 \text{ d Sm}^{-1}$ (soil E_{Ce} 0.35, 0.37 and 0.42 d Sm^{-1} at 0 – 23, 23 – 65 and 65 - 80 cm soil depth, respectively) and non-sodic $ESP \geq 15$ ($ESP = 3, 3$ and 4 for 0 – 23, 23 - 65 and 65 - 80 cm soil depth, respectively). Generally, the soil chemical fertility is low and mostly these soil deficient in nitrogen, phosphorus and organic carbon for optimum yield production of different cultivated crops. The physical and chemical properties of the soil are shown in Table 1 (LWRC, 1999).

Table 1. Some soil properties of the experimental site

Soil properties	Soil depth (cm)				
	0 – 23	23 – 65	65 - 80	80 - 105	105 – 125
FS (%)	40	23	22	21	24
CS (%)	37	33	43	42	40
Silt (%)	15	25	11	19	8
Clay (%)	8	19	24	18	28
Texture	LS	SL	SL	SL	SCL
pH (paste)	7.5	7.3	8.1	7.8	7.5
E_{Ce}	0.35	0.37	0.42	1.1	3.2
ESP	3.0	3.0	4.0	5.0	8.0
CaCO_3 (%)	0.8	2.6	10.4	0.2	27.5
O.C (%)	0.052	0.066	0.078	0.061	0.052
C/N ratio	4	4	5	5	5

LS = loamy sand, SL = sandy loam, SCL = sandy clay loam

Vigna radiate (Green gram), *Vigna sinensis* (Cowpea), *Dolichos Lablab* (Lablab bean) and *sesbania canabina* (Sesbania pea) were selected as green manure crops. These crops were planted early in the summer season (20th July) on the designated experimental units in a seed rate of 12, 18, 24 and 12 kg ha⁻¹, respectively. Also, these previous applied seed rates were doubled and tripled to find their effect on soil properties and yield of wheat. After two months from sowing and before flowering each crop was incorporated into the soil using disk plow (Figs 1 and 2). Then the soil was watered and the subsequent watering was carried out at ten-day interval for six weeks before the sowing of wheat (test crop).

Wheat variety Wadi Elneel was sown manually on 20th November 2014 and on 20th November 2015 for first and second seasons, respectively by dibbing, using seed rate of 120 kg ha⁻¹, at 0.2 m inter-row spacing. Nitrogen and phosphorus were added as recommended (86 kg N ha⁻¹ plus 43 kg P₂O₅ ha⁻¹) by (ARC). The irrigation was carried out every ten days. During all experimental period observations on grain yield of wheat were taken.

2. 1. Infiltration rate method

Infiltration rate was determined after the application of treatments and at the end of the season. A double ring infiltrometer as described by Landon (1984) was used. The two cylinders were driven into the soil to a 12 cm- depth, and then a plastic sheet was placed into the inner cylinder to prevent infiltration of water into the soil before time

Fig. 1. Green manure crop *Vigna sinensis* (Cowpea) two months after sowing.

Fig. 2. Green manure crop incorporation.

zero. At time zero the plastic sheet was removed and the rate of water height drop was measured.

2. 2. Soil moisture retention method

Composite soil samples were collected from the top 30 cm of the soil surface using an auger from each experimental unit for soil moisture retention after the termination of the experiment immediately after harvesting (at the laboratories of the Faculty of Agricultural Studies, Sudan University for Science and Technology). In the method used, two types of pressure plates were used; 1 bar and 15 bar ceramic plates, compressors giving pressure up to 250 psi, air- tight extractors, and two manifold assemblies, with valves and gauges, one operating up to 15 psi and the other in the range 15 to 250 psi (Klute, 1986).

In the procedure, saturated soil is placed in a closed chamber, subjected to the required air pressure and allowed to stand while water is forced out of it through the porous plate to a graduated burette outside the chamber. After equilibrium has been reached, the moisture content of the sample is determined by oven- drying at 105 °C for 24 hours. The pressures used included 0.3, 5, 10, and 15 bar (4.5 - 220 psi) corresponding to pF 2.5-4.2.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3. 1. Climate

Table 2, shows the average of some climatic parameters of the experimental site for the first and second seasons from National Institute of Desert Studies Meteorological Station. It is

clear that the second season was characterized by lower temperature in November, December and January compared to the first season. Also, the second season was more humid than the first season. High temperature at the beginning and the end of the growing season is a normal phenomenon. Management practices such as mulching, deep plowing can help, partly at least, in the provision of less stressed environment for crop growth and productivity.

Table 2. Climatic parameters of the experimental site in 2014/15 (1st) and 2015/16 (2nd) seasons in the Northern State, Sudan.

	Max. temp. (°C)		Min. temp. (°C)		Relative humidity (%)	
	Seasons		Seasons		Seasons	
	1 st	2 nd	1 st	2 nd	1 st	2 nd
November	33.7	31.3	16.2	9.8	46	49
December	28.8	26.3	12.6	10.1	50	53
January	29.0	26.3	9.4	8.2	51	55
February	30.4	31.1	12.1	12.2	43	44
March	36.1	37.6	16.5	17.4	34	28

Source: (National Institute of Desert Studies Meteorological Station).

3. 2. Biomass production by green manure crops two months after sowing and before flowering (g m⁻²)

Table 3. shows the average biomass production by green manure crops two months after sowing and before being incorporated into the soil for both seasons.

Table 3. Biomass production by green manure crops two months after sowing and before flowering (g m⁻²).

Seed rate levels	Green manure types	First season	Second season
First level	Lablab bean (24 kgha ⁻¹)	68 ^d	93 ^d
	Green gram (12 kgha ⁻¹)	428 ^c	533 ^{abc}
	Cowpea (18 kgha ⁻¹)	449 ^c	441 ^{bc}
	Sesbania pea (12 kgha ⁻¹)	625 ^a	489 ^{bc}

Second level	Lablab bean (48 kg ha^{-1})	62 ^d	106 ^d
	Green gram (24 kg ha^{-1})	460 ^c	557 ^{ab}
	Cowpea (36 kg ha^{-1})	406 ^c	424 ^c
	Sesbania pea (24 kg ha^{-1})	647 ^a	517 ^{abc}
Third level	Lablab bean (72 kg ha^{-1})	54 ^d	89 ^d
	Green gram (36 kg ha^{-1})	551 ^b	620 ^a
	Cowpea (54 kg ha^{-1})	439 ^c	497 ^{bc}
	Sesbania pea (36 kg ha^{-1})	674 ^a	617 ^a
	C.V	7.08	14.68
	SE \pm	16.58	23.13

A = types of green manure crops. B = seed rate levels of green manure crops.
Means followed by different letters in the same column are significantly different at $P \leq 0.05$.

The result showed that there is very highly significant differences ($p \leq 0.001$) among the types of the green manure crops in the two seasons. But, there were no significant differences among the seed rate levels of the green manure crops. This may be due to the plant competition for light, moisture, and nutrients at a high seed rate. The highest biomass was obtained by sesbania pea (on the average 649 gm^{-2}) followed by green gram (on the average 480 gm^{-2}) and cowpea (on the average 432 gm^{-2}) and the lowest one by lablab bean (on the average 62 gm^{-2}) in season one, but in season two the highest biomass produced by green gram (on the average 570 gm^{-2}) followed by sesbania pea (on the average 541 gm^{-2}) and cowpea (on the average 454 gm^{-2}) and the lowest was obtained by lablab bean (on the average 96 gm^{-2}). The best types of green manure crop are green gram, sisbania pea and cowpea.

3. 3. Infiltration rate (cm hr⁻¹)

Figs. 3 and 4. shows the infiltration rate for the control and the effect of green manure treatments for both seasons. The rate started higher from about 14 - 23 cm hr⁻¹ and then decreased clearly and progressively down the profile to about 1.4 - 4 cm hr⁻¹.

The result showed that the highest rates during all time was recorded for the control, while the lowest was found for green manure treatment. Figs. 3 & 4 revealed that green manuring treatments positively decreased the final infiltration rate from 4 $cmha^{-1}$ in season one and 3 $cmha^{-1}$ in season two for the control to 1.4 – 2.7 $cmhr^{-1}$ for the green manure treatments. The studied green manures can be ranked according to their positive effect in decreasing the final infiltration rate as follows: the sisbania pea treatments, green gram, cowpea and lastly the lablab bean treatments for both seasons. Fig. 5. shows the wetting front for the control and the effect of green manure treatments for both seasons. The result showed that the deepest wetting front was recorded for the control (58 cm in season one and 56 cm in season two) and the lowest for the green gram treatments (41 cm).

Fig. 3. Average infiltration rate for the control and the effect of green manure after harvesting (season 1).

Fig. 4. Average infiltration rate for the control and the effect of green manure after harvesting (season 2).

Fig. 5. Average wetting front (cm) for the control and the effect of green manure after harvesting.

The reduction in water infiltration rate as a result of addition of the green manure could be attributed to the increase in the moisture retention in the root zone which decrease the deep percolation and wetting front depth.

3. 4. Soil water retention

The curves are drawn by plotting the % volumetric water (Θ) against suction (Ψ_m). Volumetric water content is obtained by multiplying the moisture weight by soil density. Water retention characteristics of effect of green manure at different pressure are presented in Figs. 6 and 7. The moisture content of all treatments except the control and lablab bean treatments when plotted against suction equivalent to (0.3 to 15 bar) have shown a rapid decrease in moisture content between 0.3 and 5 bar. The general shape of all curves indicates that as the moisture content (Θ) decreases binding of water becomes stronger, and the water retained between 0.3 and 15 bar is of special interest as it is considered to represent the amount of water available to plant. It correlates well with the moisture remaining in the soil under field conditions, 2-3 days after irrigation. However, a number of limitations might be considered in the evaluation of plant available water. Table 4. shows that the green manure increased soil available water (soil equivalent depth) as compared with the control. In the first season the lowest value (14 mm) of available soil water was recorded for the control and lablab bean treatments and the highest (31 mm) on green gram (12 kg ha⁻¹) and cowpea (18 kg ha⁻¹) treatments. In the second season the lowest value (20 mm) of available soil water recorded for the control and lablab bean treatments and the highest (30 mm) on green manure treatments (the third level) except Lablab bean treatment.

Fig. 6. Water retention curves of the effect of green manure and the control between 0.3 and 15 bar tension as a function of volumetric water content (season 1).

Fig. 7. Water retention curves of the effect of green manure and the control between 0.3 and 15 bar tension as a function of volumetric water content (season 2).

The available soil water recorded on the first level of organic manures not far from that recorded for the second and the third levels of organic manures. The improvement of soil moisture retention in response to application of organic manures has already been reported by Mosavi *et al.* (2012) and Cercioglu *et al.* (2014) who reported that organic manures improved the soil moisture retention.

Table 4. Effect of green and green manures on soil moisture equivalent depth (30 cm) of available Water (mm) in the Northern State, Sudan.

Levels	Treatments	First season			Second season		
		$\frac{1}{3}$ bar (mm)	15bar (mm)	Av. Water (mm)	$\frac{1}{3}$ bar (mm)	15 bar (mm)	Av. Water (mm)
	Control	34	20	14	36	16	20
First level	Lablab bean (24 kg ha ⁻¹)	33	19	14	38	18	20
	Green gram (12kg ha ⁻¹)	43	17	26	46	17	29
	Cowpea (18 kg ha ⁻¹)	48	17	31	42	17	25
	Sesbania pea (12 kg ha ⁻¹)	48	17	31	42	17	25
Second level	Lablab bean (48 kg ha ⁻¹)	37	23	14	42	24	18
	Green gram (24kg ha ⁻¹)	43	17	26	42	17	25
	Cowpea (54 kg ha ⁻¹)	47	21	26	51	21	30
	Sesbania pea (24 kg ha ⁻¹)	43	17	26	47	17	30
Third level	Lablab bean (72 kg ha ⁻¹)	37	23	14	42	19	23
	Green gram (36 kg ha ⁻¹)	43	17	26	42	12	30
	Cowpea (54 kg ha ⁻¹)	47	21	26	42	12	30
	Sesbania pea (36 kg ha ⁻¹)	47	21	26	42	12	30

3. 5. Grain yield of wheat crop

The results in Table 5. showed that there were no significant differences for the grain yield of wheat among the levels of green manure in all seasons. However there were very highly

significant differences ($P \leq 0.001$) in grain yield among the control and the types of green manure except lablab bean treatments.

In this study the control was recorded lower grain yield ranges from 0.51 and 0.92 ton ha⁻¹ for the first and second seasons. Then lablab bean treatments ranged from 0.91 to 1.38 ton ha⁻¹ in both seasons, which is not far from that of the control and the other types of green manure ranged between 2.33 to 4.20 ton ha⁻¹.

Generally, the second season obtained higher grain yield than that of the first season. This result might be due to the variations in climatic conditions between the two seasons, i.e. the second season was characterized by lower temperature in December and January and higher relative humidity percentage in all months compared to the first season, and the first season was characterized by higher temperature in February and March compared to the second season (Table 2). High temperature is a major environmental constraint that limits wheat production in the Sudan (Ageeb 1994).

The data in all Tables and Figures showed that green gram, cowpea and sesbania pea have a relative advantage over lablab bean in improving the some physical soil properties and increased grain yield of wheat.

This is probably acceptable because these three types of green manure crop (the best types of green manure crop) have a relatively higher biomass production (432 gm⁻² to 649 gm⁻²) in this study compared to that of lablab bean (62 gm⁻² to 96 gm⁻²) (Table 2). Figures 8 and 9 illustrate the appearance of wheat crop under the control treatment and the best of green manure treatment, respectively. It clear that the growth and appearance of wheat crop grown under green manure treatment was more better than under the controlled treatment.

Fig. 8. Appearance of Wheat Crop Grown under the Controlled Treatments.

Fig. 9. Appearance of Wheat Crop Grown under Application of green manure.

High wheat grain yield due to application of organic fertilizers is reported by Rasul *et al.* (2015) and Ahmed *et al.* (2011) they found that green manure significantly increased grain yield of wheat crop.

Table 5. Effect of green manure on grain yield of wheat (tonha⁻¹)

Seed rates levels	Types of Green manure	First season	Second season
	Control	0.51 ^c	0.92 ^b
First level	L (24 kgha ⁻¹)	0.92 ^{bc}	1.34 ^b
	G (12 kgha ⁻¹)	2.35 ^a	4.10 ^a
	C (18 kgha ⁻¹)	2.40 ^a	3.94 ^a
	S (12 kgha ⁻¹)	2.51 ^a	3.81 ^a
Second level	L (48 kgha ⁻¹)	0.91 ^{bc}	1.38 ^b
	G (24 kgha ⁻¹)	2.29 ^a	4.00 ^a
	C (36 kgha ⁻¹)	2.45 ^a	4.10 ^a

	S (24 kgha ⁻¹)	2.44 ^a	3.96 ^a
Third level	L (72 kgha ⁻¹)	1.04 ^{bc}	1.10 ^b
	G (36 kgha ⁻¹)	2.43 ^a	4.20 ^a
	C (54 kgha ⁻¹)	2.33 ^a	4.20 ^a
	S (36 kgha ⁻¹)	2.35 ^a	4.00 ^a
	Grand mean	1.91	3.15
	C.V	12.12	19.65
	SE±	0.134	0.357

L = Lablab bean, G = Green gram, C = Cowpea, S = Sesbania pea

Means followed by different letters in the same column are significantly different at $P \leq 0.05$.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The results showed that soil infiltration rate, soil moisture retention and wheat yield were improved due to application of GM. Therefore, GM may be used in vast areas, as it may pose a solution to the problems of the infertility of desert plain soils and unavailability of organic manure. It is recommended that Green gram (12 kg ha⁻¹), Cowpea (18 kg ha⁻¹) and Sesbania pea (12 kg ha⁻¹) which are available and cheaper are suitable types of green manure crops for soil reclamation of the desert soils of Sudan.

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